

**Decarbonizing the lime-based construction materials industry:
A practical guide for cradle-to-gate life cycle inventory**

Agustin Laveglia^{a,b,*}, Neven Ukrainczyk^a, Nele De Belie^b, Eddie Koenders^a

^a *Institute of Construction and Building Materials, Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, TU Darmstadt, Franziska-Braun-Straße 3, 64287, Darmstadt, Germany*

^b *Magnel-Vandepitte Laboratory for Structural Engineering and Building Materials, Ghent University, Technologiepark Zwijnaarde 60, B-9052 Ghent, Belgium*

* Corresponding author laveglia@wib.tu-darmstadt.de

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an integral parametrized framework to calculate the life-cycle inventory (LCI) in lime-based construction materials manufacturing, utilized for implementing decarbonization strategies in the LCI. The calcination operation is identified as the main source of CO₂ emissions, with 0.79 tCO₂/t CaO being inevitable (65% of total emissions). Kiln fuel combustion contributes up to 35% to emissions. Decarbonization strategies are ranked as: carbon capture, carbon direct avoidance, and circular economy. Parallel Flow Regenerative Kilns result in 40% lower energy consumption compared to Long Rotary Kilns. Substituting lignite with natural gas can reduce emissions by up to 17%. Direct CO₂ separation from calcite decomposition, coupled with thermal energy recovery, can capture 65% of the CO₂ emitted, reducing kiln energy consumption by 15% and CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion by 13%. The high purity of captured CO₂ offers potential for future use as a valuable by-product. Supplementary raw materials in lime-based binder production have limited effects on CO₂ emissions due to unavoidable emissions from calcite decomposition. The proposed process-oriented parametric methodology empowers Life Cycle Assessment practitioners, reducing reliance on generic databases for rigorous and transparent inventory calculations.

Keywords: sustainability; lime-based materials; life cycle inventory; process-oriented methodology; circular economy.

Abbreviations

ASK	Annular Shaft Kiln
BAT	Best Available Technologies
CDST	Calix's Direct Separation Technology
CCT	Carbon Capture Technologies
EU	European Union
FU	Functional Unit
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HL	Hydrated Lime
IEA	International Energy Agency
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LBM	Lime Based Materials
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LRK	Long Rotatory Kiln
MFSK	Mixed Feed Shaft Kiln
POM	Process Oriented Methodology
PFRK	Parallel Flow Regenerative Kilns
PRK	Preheater Rotary Kiln
PMS	Paper mill sludge, before treatment
PMS-D	Paper mill sludge, calcined
RHL	Recycled Hydrated Lime
SCS-CCT	Smart Carbon Separation and Carbon Capture Technologies
UPMI	Unit Process Mass Inventory
UPEI	Unit Process Energy Inventory

Symbols

ΔH_x°	Enthalpy standard of formation, x represents the compound, in kJ/mol
$\dot{m}_x$	Mass flow, x represents the specific compound
E_{total}	Total Energy Requirement
$E_{transformation}$	Energy requirement of a transformation (physical/chemical)
$E_{operation}$	Energy requirement to operate the device, in MJ
Q, Q_{H_2O}, Q_{CO_2}	Heat release, in KJ
$Q_{H_2O(l)latent}$	Latent heat of vaporization (water), in kJ
$Q_{H_2O(l)sensible}$	Sensible heat, liquid water, in kJ
$Q_{H_2O(v)sensible}$	Sensible heat, vapor water, in kJ
$Q_{CO_2(g)sensible}$	Sensible heat, gaseous carbon dioxide, in kJ
cp_x	Specific heat capacity, x represents the compound, in kJ/kg K
ΔT	Change of temperatures, in K.
λ_v	Specific latent heat, in kJ/kg
γ	Substitution Potential
η^{sr}	Efficiency of the intermediate treatment
$\alpha^{sr:disp}$	Substitutability, sr: secondary resource, disp: displaced resource
R_p^{sr}	Resource potential of the secondary resource

1. INTRODUCTION

Life Cycle Assessment methodology [1] has been applied to cement-based materials to calculate the environmental consequences of manufacturing different types of concrete with a wide variety of supplementary binders and/or applying different types of aggregates and additives [2]–[9]. However, studies related to the environmental impact of lime-based materials are less developed. During the last six decades the amount of produced cement has increased about 30 times, while the world's population grew only by a factor 3 [10]–[12]. Consequently, many resources have been invested mostly in designing more eco-efficient concretes rather than other construction materials. However, lime is widely utilized in new constructions, from concrete blocks to plasters and mortars, as well as in the preservation of cultural heritage. [13].

The production of quicklime (CaO), the main precursor of these materials, in 2020 amounted to 20 Mt/y, with the construction sector representing 19% of the market [14] [15]. Its production emits 1.2 t CO₂/t of CaO, meaning that in Europe in one single year 4.6 Mt of CO₂ are generated only because of CaO production [16]. These emissions contribute to around 1% of the global anthropogenic emissions and have two main sources or origin: chemical decomposition of limestone (aprox. 65% of the total) and other process emissions [17]–[19]. The European regulations require industries to adapt their production systems and technologies to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 in response to the environmental crisis. The urgency to act is increasing due to the European Trading System's carbon price of 90 € per metric ton of carbon (2022) for emissions generated by industries, which has increased by 9 times from 2018, making the economic motivation as important as the environmental one [20].

Rather than being a problem, the decarbonization of the lime-based construction materials industry can be an opportunity that provides the sector with a competitive advantage. There are five main points that are essential to achieving this goal: (1) power the manufacturing process with eco-efficient energy sources (such as biomass or electricity); (2) implement the concept of circular economy to minimise raw materials extraction; (3) change current technologies by using more efficient kilns with direct emission separation technologies; (4) implement carbon capture technologies; (5) combine point 3 and 4 to transform CO₂ from an emission into a co-product. Last point is critical, because it can lead to minimize emissions per ton of produced material, along with a potential added revenue from the reduced cost of emissions and from selling CO₂ as by-product to other industries. By implementing these integral and interactive strategies, combined with the natural effect of carbonation during the use phase, it is possible to improve the overall sustainability performance of lime-based materials, while reaching even a carbon negative scenario.

To illustrate potential scenarios, in Figure 1 a scheme is provided showing as an example the carbon profile of a lime-based render over its entire life cycle. In both cases, a binder consisting of a mix of hydrated lime and cement is used, along with aggregates and additives to manufacture a dry rendered powder. In the “business-as-usual” scenario, hydrated lime is produced in a traditional way, using limestone as the main raw material, and solid fossils as the main fuel in the lime kiln representing an energy supply with a limited amount of renewable sources. Over the life cycle, the material naturally absorbs CO₂ from the environment in a process known as carbonation [21]–[23]. Even though this use phase could be considered as a carbon sink, the room for improvement is rather limited at this stage and relying on this carbonation phase to achieve carbon neutrality is far from realistic.

The manufacturing stage has such high levels of emissions that even if the material could fully carbonate during its life cycle, it would be unable to offset all cradle-to-gate emissions. However, in a scenario of enhanced sustainability, by-products and/or waste materials are utilized as

raw materials whilst supplying the same functionality to a mix as hydrated lime. Eco-efficient energy sources are utilized to power the devices and carbon capture technologies are implemented in such a way that not only CO₂ is captured but also employed to prepare a co-product that can substitute part of the energy requirements of the limekiln. In this case, the same rate of carbonation is considered as for the business-as-usual scenario, while carbon neutrality and even carbon negative are more plausible.

Figure 1. Carbon profile of a lime-based render over its life cycle under a business-as-usual and an enhanced sustainability scenario.

For a more sustainable scenario to take place, a change in mindset is required and accurate information to support decision making is mandatory. One of the main problems to face is the lack of environmental impact studies in this area, because so far only a few research articles have addressed the environmental profiles through LCA ([13], [24]–[27]). These studies are mainly focused on the effect of mix designs on the environmental impact through generic databases while no assessment of materials manufacturing is done. A rather complete research article (and one of the very few) on decarbonization of the lime industry describes processes and carbon capture technologies but does not address the opportunities of circular economy for LBM and the particularities on how to evaluate them through life cycle assessment [28]. All in all, the limited research on sustainability assessment of lime-based materials indicates a significant knowledge gap, posing challenges for stakeholders in making informed decisions that enhance production systems and materials design based on scientific evidence.

The assessment of decarbonization strategies in the lime-based construction materials industry requires a reliable transparent, robust and flexible life cycle inventory (LCI). While parametrized process-based life cycle inventory has been used in evaluating scenarios at the building scale (e.g., operational energy and environmental flows), there is a need for further development of an LCI design specifically tailored to the challenges of producing sustainable construction materials [29]–[31]. Currently, the energy use in kiln technology and energy sources contributes up to 35% of CO₂ emissions in lime production, making it crucial to explore alternatives for significant reductions [16]. However, limitations arise from the inability to modify existing datasets in commercial databases used for modeling building materials production, hampering the implementation of

different scenarios. Additionally, while carbon capture technologies hold promises for emission reduction in the industry, the lack of depth in inventory calculation and insufficient framework support [29], [32]–[34], raise concerns about inventory quality and potential missed opportunities for additional credits achievable through a parametrized inventory approach.

In building materials manufacturing, the scarcity of resources due to extensive raw material consumption is a critical issue. Circular economy emerges as an alternative to reduce resource extraction and waste landfilling. Nevertheless, the environmental impact of using waste-based materials as replacements for cement/lime needs careful evaluation. Currently, it is common practice to overlook the environmental impact of their production or omit reporting the intermediate treatments required for their use as supplementary materials [35]–[38]. Properly assessing their contribution in the manufacturing phase requires a comprehensive inventory considering intermediate treatments, integrating material physical and chemical properties, materials flows and energy requirements. Moreover, in the dynamic context of advancing technologies and energy sources, there are multiple alternatives to analyze for enhanced sustainability. Implementing these alternatives while ensuring robust and transparent assessment of scenarios can be facilitated by a parametrized inventory approach.

This paper presents an integral parametrized framework to calculate the life-cycle inventory (LCI) in lime-based construction materials manufacturing, utilized for implementing decarbonization strategies in the LCI. Three decarbonization strategies are studied: carbon direct avoidance, carbon capture and circular economy. The application of this methodology is demonstrated through three case studies. First, the inventory calculation of a single unit process in hydrated lime manufacturing is presented, allowing for a parametric study on different kiln technologies and energy sources. Second, the inventory calculation includes a CO₂ capture system with energy recovery in the lime kiln. Lastly, the modeling of the intermediate treatment of paper mill sludge as supplementary lime material in hydrated lime manufacturing is illustrated, along with an equation to determine the maximum substitution amount.

2. Methodology

2.1. Main framework of the life cycle assessment methodology applied to building materials

According to the ISO Standard 14044:2006 [39], there are four main steps to be considered in LCA: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, life-cycle impact analysis and interpretation of the results [1], [39]. This paper is specifically focused on the life cycle inventory modelling of the cradle-to-gate production, in which all the emissions as a result of the materials transformation to obtain the products take place. However, when aiming at decarbonization in the context of lime-based materials it is relevant to see how all stages of the life cycle of a material can influence the overall environmental performance. The different phases are well established in the CEN TC350 standards for the case of a complete life cycle of buildings [40], while not all of them are directly applicable when the scope is to analyse a single material or a combination of them. As shown in Figure 2A, the system boundaries are organized in 4 modules: (A) Product Stage and Construction Process; (B) Use Stage; (C) End of life Stage; and (D) Benefits beyond the system boundaries.

A modified proposal covering the scope of the CEN TC350 is presented in Figure 2B, to specifically consider in the life cycle the potential impact of carbon capture technologies on the manufacturing stage (A4) and the carbon sequestration during the use phase (B1) [41]. With regards to the use stage, carbon sequestration (B1) acquires a high relevance in lime-based materials, in contrast to what happens in cement-based materials. The main benefits of lime-based materials are that the carbonation proceeds in general faster than in cement-based materials and it is not unwanted phenomena like in concrete, which can lead to the corrosion of the reinforcement, increasing the

need for maintenance (B2). In Module C, C1 is mainly focussing on the deconstruction approach rather than the traditional demolition. Finally, aiming at highlighting the importance of the circular economy, Module D is relocated at the bottom of the figure showing how each stage of the life cycle can interact with this module.

Figure 2. Scope of the LCA of buildings according to CEN TC350 standards [40] and modified scope of the LCA in lime-based materials.

In this paper we propose a methodology to calculate a parametric life cycle inventory to be applied in the production stage A of building materials (Figure 2). During this phase it is necessary to determine the energy requirements (i.e., to power a device), material inputs (raw materials and ancillary inputs as well as other physical inputs) and material outputs (products, co-products, and waste; and emissions to air, water, and soil) normalized per functional unit [1].

Inventory modelling is crucial in LCA as it affects the accuracy of impact calculations. To obtain reliable results on the impact of decarbonization strategies for the lime industry, rigorous calculation of the inventory is essential. With regards to the data, a distinction between foreground data and background data should be made. The first are data from a foreground system of primary concern to the analyst. It can be collected, measured, calculated, or estimated to quantify inputs and outputs of a unit process (i.e., the specific electricity consumption of a device used in a unit process).

Background data in LCA consist of aggregated energy and materials inputs to the foreground system, without specifying individual plants or operations. Generic databases like EcoInvent [42] and Gabi are widely used for process modelling in the construction materials sector [7] due to their comprehensiveness. However, many datasets are unavailable, nonmodifiable or lack transparency,

making it challenging to identify the specific unit processes and estimation sources. As a result, environmental scientists and LCA practitioners often have to rely on the provided data without the ability to make modifications or fully understand its origins.

Applying a process-oriented parametric methodology for life cycle inventory modelling can enhance transparency and results reliability. This approach, outlined in ISO Standard 14044 [1], involves calculating inputs and outputs through mass and energy balances, validating and refining them with first-hand data. However, it is not widely used in the LCA community due to the need for process engineering expertise to ensure coherence in decision-making and calculations. The subsequent sections will provide a concise overview of the fundamental steps for constructing an inventory based on process calculations.

Figure 3. The process-oriented methodology for calculating the cradle-to-gate life cycle inventory of a manufacturing process and specific parts: the presented workflow is demonstrated in each case study.

2.2 Process-oriented methodology to calculate the life cycle inventory

The procedure of process-oriented design of LCI is shown in Figure 3. The main parts of the diagram are numbered for a better identification. The calculation methodology of the Unit Process Mass Inventory (UPMI) and Unit Process Energy Inventory (UPEI) is a general guideline to build the parametrized LCI. The aggregation of both constitutes the LCI of the calculated unit process. With respect to the UPMI, a specific substitution modelling approach is proposed when waste or by-products are used as supplementary lime materials. For simplicity, in the Results section the most relevant calculation steps for each case study are shown. Figure 3 also shows where the focus has been placed in each case study.

A. General calculation of a unit process

After determining the goal and scope of the study, manufacturing process, functional unit and unit operations, the mass inventory, followed by the energy inventory, are calculated.

- *Calculation of the Unit Process Mass Inventory*

In the traditional cradle-to-gate scenario (i.e., no circular economy included), the calculation starts by identifying the physical/chemical transformation taking place in each unit. Physical transformations are those in which the chemical composition of matter remains unaltered (such as a size reduction operation, washing or drying). Usually, simple mass balances can be used to determine the flows. On the contrary, whenever the chemistry of material is modified, a chemical transformation takes place (i.e., limestone calcination). This information serves to establish the mass or energy balances that provide the set of equations to define every mass flow on the unit. These flows can be either emissions or intermediate/final products. The aggregated material flows constitute the Unit Process Mass Inventory (UPMI).

- *Calculation of the Unit Process Energy Inventory*

The Unit Process Energy Inventory (UPEI) can only be calculated after the UPMI. The first reason behind this, is that the energy requirements are attached to the amount of material that needs to be processed (i.e., the energy demand is normalized to the mass flows). The second reason is that in many cases, there are interchanges of energy as result of chemical reactions or changes of state, which can be credited to the overall energy demand of the unit process.

The energy requirements depend on the physical or chemical process carried out and, on the technology used. The total energy consumption (Eq. 1) in the unit process can be expressed as:

$$E_{total} = E_{transformation} + E_{operation} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

With regards to the first term $E_{transformation}$, the transformation of the materials involves interchange of energy (change of state, formation of new compounds, etc.). It is always helpful to model these processes using the chemical reactions or state change involved and using tabulated enthalpy data. The transformation energy needs to be complemented by the operational energy ($E_{operation}$), which is mostly defined by the type of device (i.e., technology) and its efficiency.

Naturally, it is always a good practice to validate the data with literature and producers (Point 4 in Fig. 3). The application of these steps, leads to a quantification of materials and energy required per functional unit in the inventory (Point 5).

B. Use of supplementary materials in the cradle-to-gate production

When it comes to sustainable production and consumption, there are two problems to be addressed: the generation of waste and the consumption of virgin raw materials. The final disposal of waste materials is the less preferred option according to the waste hierarchy. Therefore, recycling waste materials for the manufacturing of valuable products under the so-called circular economy, emerges as a significant alternative to solve both problems [43]. Under this paradigm, there are at least two life cycles to consider: LC1 which generates the waste material/by-product (e.g., paper mill sludge) and the LC2 in which the determining product (e.g., lime-based plaster) is manufactured. The connection between both life cycles is what we call intermediate treatment, which has the function to treat the material to give a certain degree of equivalence between the displacing material and the material that will be displaced. The degree of equivalence is based on the substitution/system expansion concept, under which two or more products are considered interchangeable alternatives to fulfil a specific function [44].

The proposed methodology goes from a feasibility analysis of using the secondary material to the calculation of the substitution potential, linking the initial properties of the waste with the final properties required for the substitution. This methodology can be applied to model the inventory of a wide variety of waste treatments, independent of its initial properties. The availability of such datasets in generic databases is rather limited and by applying this approach the LCA practitioner can be independent of them. Moreover, given that the LCI is parametrized, it is also possible to evaluate different technologies and energy sources to power the devices. Further explanation of the steps for the application of the methodology is given below.

- Feasibility analysis and waste or by-product provider data collection

The feasibility analysis includes the production process of the potential provider of the supplementary material and a market analysis to determine if the material should be considered as a waste or must be considered as a by-product. According to the EU directive 2008/98EC to qualify for the by-product status the following conditions should be met: *(a) further use of the substance is certain (e.g., as cement replacement); (b) the substance or object is produced as an integral part of a production process; (c) the substance or object can be used directly without any further processing other than industrial normal practise; and (d) further use is lawful* [45]. Therefore, part of the environmental impact associated to the production process should be somehow allocated to the by-products as well. However, if the material is usually disposed or if it does not have any economic value, the material can be considered as a waste and no allocation is required.

Furthermore, the local availability of the waste should be determined. On the one hand the rate of generation of the waste of interest by the first cycle process, should be sufficient to satisfy a predefined demand. On the other hand, the production plant of the first cycle process should be at a reasonable distance from the production plant of the determining product.

- Determine the properties of the waste (or by-product)

Along with the feasibility analysis, a waste or by-product can be introduced in the LC2 if its properties are to some extent related to the properties of the material that they would displace. Among relevant physical properties are identified the state (solid or liquid), density, humidity (if solid), average particle size (if solid); while chemical properties include chemical and mineralogical composition, pH, content of organics, etc.

- Determine the functionality performance

When looking for alternatives to replace the original materials, it is important to have clarity about the function they are fulfilling in the system. The aim of the supplementary material is to replace one of the original materials in the inventory. Therefore, the properties of the waste or by product should help to identify which material can be potentially substituted, according to a certain function that the original material provides. The functionality performance is an integral concept that requires the identification of a property of interest, in clear connection with the material that will be replaced and representative of it.

- Design the intermediate treatment

The intermediate treatment requires the selection and design (in the same way as described in Section 2.2 A) of the unit processes required to transform chemically or physically the waste or by-product in order to produce the secondary material that will be used as substitute. The design is linked to the definition of the functionality performance and generally would require scientific data as inputs for the design (calcination temperatures, materials, fineness requirements, etc.).

- Potential Substitution Calculation

The Equation 2 is inspired on the work by Vadenbo et al. [44] but the concepts behind the parameters are redesigned and adapted to be used in construction materials. The Equation can be used to calculate the potential amount of a specific resource that can be substituted (γ , in the Equation 1). [47]

$$\gamma = \alpha^{sr:disp} \cdot R_p^{sr} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The Equation integrates the data previously collected, considering the following technical aspects:

Substitutability ($\alpha^{sr:disp}$): is the link between the materials properties, the treatment process design and the final secondary resource that will displace the original material in the determining life cycle. The recovered resource is treated in a designed way according to the experiments performed to achieve a similar performance than the material that will be displaced. It is calculated as the ratio of a set of properties of the transformed secondary resource (sr) and the original displaced (disp) material. The degree of substitutability expresses to which extent the secondary resource can fulfil the function of the displaced material in the system.

Resource Potential (R_p^{sr}): represents the maximum amount of the secondary resource -after the intermediate treatment- that is being produced per FU of the secondary life cycle. It is important to accurately calculate the real amount that will be used as displacing product because the substitutability would only have a real effect in practise if the provision were enough in the conditions of a real plant operation. Otherwise, a benefit that cannot be provided is being accounted for.

3. Results and discussions

This section presents the results of the application of the methodology on three case studies focusing on hydrated lime production. Figure 4 illustrates which part of the production process is covered in each case-study for clarity.

The first case-study focuses on the production of CaO, a precursor for hydrated lime production. It demonstrates the calculation of the parametrized LCI for a single unit process, as outlined in Figure 3 (Section 2.2 A).

The second case study explores carbon savings and carbon capture in the production of calcium oxide, utilizing the parametrized LCI from case study 1.

Finally, case study 3 demonstrates the application of a substitution approach for a lime-based mortar production by upcycling paper mill sludge, a waste of the paper industry.

3.1 Case study 1: Calcium oxide production

Calcium oxide is the main precursor for hydrated lime manufacturing and is produced through the calcination process (Figure 4). Prior to calcination, the extraction and processing of calcite are required, involving activities such as crushing, washing, drying. While these operations are modelled using the same approach, for practicality and relevance, the methodology is applied specifically to calculate the inventory of the unit process “calcination”.

Figure 4. The flow diagram of Ca(OH)₂ production, along with the focus of each case study addressed.

Following Figure 3 (Step 1.1), as the calcination operation is being modelled, the functional unit is the production of 1 ton of calcium oxide and the system boundaries include the lime kiln, in which the chemical transformation from calcite to calcium oxide occurs. The calculation of the UPMI and UPEI is shown below.

Unit Process Mass Inventory (UPMI)

To calculate the mass flows in the unit process, the decomposition reaction of calcite in the lime kiln is first considered (Reaction 1). To produce 1 ton of CaO (FU) the amount of CaCO₃ that should be supplied, the amount of CO₂ generated and transformation energy to be supplied need to be calculated. For this calculation, the following assumptions are considered (1) 100% purity of CaCO₃, (2) 100% conversion of the reaction, (3) steady state of the process and (4) no mass accumulation in the process.

Chemical reactions increase the complexity of a process. When analysing a system with chemical reactions, we need first to determine some important factors like stoichiometric coefficients, limiting reactant, and conversion percentage. Then we can choose the material balance equations, say, mass balance or element balance. The global mass balance can be written as follows (Eq. 3).

$$m_{\text{CaCO}_3} = m_{\text{CO}_2} + m_{\text{CaO}} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

After replacing the m_{CaO} (1 ton) in the Equation 2, there are two unknowns and therefore another equation is needed. The second type of balance that can be used is by chemical elements (Ca, C and O). To apply these balances, the molecular weight of the reactants and products are used ($\text{CaCO}_3 = 100.08 \text{ g/mol}$; $\text{CaO} = 56.07 \text{ g/mol}$; $\text{CO}_2 = 44.01 \text{ g/mol}$). The balance can be done following any element, in this case Ca. Then, after making the calculations, the second equation needed to solve the system is found (Eq. 4).

$$0.0099m_{\text{CaCO}_3} = 0.0178m_{\text{CaO}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Using Equations 3 and 4 the following results are found: 1.79 t CaCO_3 /t CaO and 0.79 t CO_2 /t CaO . These results mean that the “ CaCO_3 preparation” unit process (Figure 4) should provide 1.79 t CaCO_3 to satisfy the function of the calcination process. All the material flows are now specified and can be aggregated in the UPMI.

Unit Process Energy Inventory (UPIE)

After completing the calculation of the UPMI, follows the energy inventory, which is calculated as specified in Eq. 1. Continuing with the calcium oxide production case, the term $E_{\text{transformation}}$ includes the chemical energy required for the decarbonation (Reaction 1). Here the UPMI and UPEI are integrated, because the mass flow of CaCO_3 (1,79 t) and the enthalpy of the reaction (177.3 kJ/mol CaCO_3) are used and 3160 MJ/t CaO is the calculated value for the transformation energy term.

The second term in the UPEI is the operation energy, which highly depends on the operation principle and technology. As always, first-hand data is desired, but Best Available Technologies (BAT) published by the European Commission are a comprehensive source of information for the design, from which current technologies being used in the market, types of fuels used, the direction followed by the market and specific data such as efficiencies, average energy consumptions of devices, etc. can be obtained [19]. In the case of the lime industry, Parallel Flow Regenerative Kilns (PFRK) are the most efficient current technology for the manufacturing of lime and the literature research shows a total energy consumption by these kilns (E_{total} in Eq. 4) is $3900 \pm 0.5 \text{ MJ/t CaO}$ [19], [47]–[51]. With the calculated energy of the transformation (3160 MJ/t) and the total energy consumed by the device (3900 MJ/t), the energy of operation can be obtained (Eq. 4), amounting to around $740 \pm 0.5 \text{ MJ/t}$. These values validate the calculation performed previously (Figure 3, Point 4).

Aggregated data

The aggregated inventory of the unit process “Calcination” is summarised in Table 1, including the results of the UPMI and UPEI (Figure 3, Point 5).

Table 1. Inventory to produce 1 ton of calcium oxide

INPUT	PROCESSED AMOUNT		Comments
	AMOUNT	UNIT	
CaCO ₃ from “CaCO ₃ preparation”	1.79	t	See Figure 4 (3160 MJ E _{transformation} + 740 MJ E _{operation})
PFRK Operation	3900	MJ	
OUTPUT	AMOUNT	UNIT	
CaO (determining product)	1	t	
CO ₂ (as emission)	0.79	t	Chemical decarbonation of CaCO ₃

The input CaCO₃ from “CaCO₃ preparation” brings along the environmental impact associated with all the upstream processes (from the extraction of the raw materials). An important remark is that the CO₂ produced during the calcite decomposition is accounted as an emission to the environment. Furthermore, by having the inventory parametrized, several alternatives for the decarbonation of the lime-industry can be implemented, as shown in the next case study.

3.2 Case study 2: Carbon savings/capture in the lime-industry

In the previous section, through the inventory calculation of the kiln, the case study evidences one of the main reasons for the high CO₂ emissions of the lime industry, namely decarbonation of limestone (0,79 tCO₂/t CaO). The second main reason are the emissions associated to the combustion of the fuels, which provide the energy for the chemical transformation. The mitigation of both impacts requires different strategies and here we show how the parametrized LCI calculated in Section 3.1 can help to assess these alternatives. The main focus of this case study is then in the UPEI component of the inventory (Figure 3, Step 3). First, we discuss carbon direct avoidance as a mean to reduce the emissions of the fuel’s combustion, which basically is oriented to the transition to more eco efficient energy sources [16]. Second, to reduce the emissions of the calcite decarbonation, a combination of improved kiln technologies coupled with energy recovery and carbon capture system is presented. Under this approach, CO₂ can be captured by a certain technology and furthermore be sold to vertical-related markets [52], [53].

3.2.1 Carbon direct avoidance

Carbon direct avoidance (CDA) requires the use of improved technologies in the lime kilns as well as eco-efficient fuels as energy source. The question that arises is how to include both scenarios in the parametrized LCI, because they will have a direct effect on the UPEI. To discuss this case study, we start from the parametrized LCI calculated in Table 1 and, particularly focus, on the E_{operation} term of the UPEI. More efficient kilns can reduce the heat loss through the walls of the kiln, can improve the efficiency of the fuel use and overall reduce the specific energy demand of the kiln (MJ/kg of product). The last point is of direct interest for the UPEI, as basically different specific heat demands are obtained for each technology.

Some kiln technologies used for quicklime production are shown in Figure 5. The Figure shows the contribution of the E_{transformation} and E_{operation} in the total energy demand (MJ/t) of each kiln (Eq. 4). Here it is observed that the contribution of the transformation energy is equal in all technologies, but the operational energy differs because all of the kilns have different efficiency. The minimum total energy demand is found for the PFRK kiln, which also explains why in Europe this is the preferred technology. Compared to the less efficient kiln LRK, around 40% reduction in the total energy is achieved. Both technologies can be implemented in the parametrized LCI by changing the PFRK

operation line (heat requirement) in Table 1 from 3900 to around 6100 MJ/t on average. In this way, the effect of different technologies on the inventory can be analysed. A decrement in the heat requirement, will definitely lead to carbon direct emission avoidance. However, the exact values depend on the fuel mix used in the kiln because they have different CO₂ intensity per unit of energy released [16].

Moving towards eco-efficient fuels is a must to reduce the emissions, by minimizing the use of fossil fuels (hard coal, lignite, and petrol coke) [54]. According to EuLA report 2019 they represented around 51% of the fuel mix in the European Lime industry [48]. The main problem associated with fossil fuels is their high carbon intensity factor: 103.8 tCO₂/TJ for lignite, 74 tCO₂/TJ for light fuel oil and 55.9 tCO₂/TJ for natural gas [55]. The parametrized inventory developed in Table 1 helps to evaluate different energy sources, because different datasets can be selected from the used database (e.g., Ecoinvent) to model the production of the energy. Considering the energy demand of the PFRK (3900 MJ) and the carbon intensity factors of each fuel, different scenarios of fuel mixes can be evaluated, as shown in Table 2. For instance, if the used fuel is lignite or natural gas, it would lead to 0.23tCO₂/tCaO and 0.41 tCO₂/tCaO respectively (44% increment). These scenarios are shown in Table 2. As can be observed in the Table, in the case of the use of natural gas, a total of 1.02 tCO₂/tCaO are generated and 1.2 tCO₂/tCaO for lignite. If natural gas is used instead of lignite, a 17% of carbon avoidance is obtained.

Figure 5. Contribution of the $E_{transformation}$ and $E_{operation}$ to the total Heat demand in lime kilns (based on [19] and previous calculations).

Table 2. Inventory to produce 1 ton of calcium oxide: Effect of two different energy sources

INPUT	FUEL: LIGNITE		FUEL: NATURAL GAS		Comments
	AMOUNT	UNIT	AMOUNT	UNIT	
CaCO ₃ from “CaCO ₃ preparation”	1.79	t	1.79	t	See Figure 4
PFRK Operation	3900	MJ	3900	MJ	(3160 MJ $E_{transformation}$ + 740 MJ $E_{operation}$)
OUTPUT	AMOUNT	UNIT	AMOUNT	UNIT	
CaO (determining product)	1	t	1	t	
CO ₂ (as emission)	0.79	t	0.79	t	Decarbonation of CaCO ₃
CO ₂ (as emission)	0.41	t	0.23	t	Fuel combustion

Naturally, when building the LCI, coherent decisions regarding what is possible should be made. In principle, there is a mandate from the European Commission to reduce emissions in the building materials sector and therefore measures should be taken accordingly. However, the way in which they can be reduced is subjected to the availability of resources in each country. Not all countries can achieve this goal in the same way, and this should be reflected in the LCI.

For the specific case of the effect of changing the energy sources to power a production system of hydrated lime, the reader is referred to a previous work of the authors[16]. In this work, a parametrized inventory of the plant was calculated following the methodology in Figure 3. The environmental impact of current and potential future energy sources used for hydrated lime production was calculated and the implementation of the scenario analysis in the parametrized LCI follows the same principle as explained before. The research was complemented by a geographic localization of the plant in which the availability of different energy sources was thoroughly analysed. It was found that as the proportion of fossil solid fuel decreases and natural gas and biomass increases in the fuel mix, a reduction of up to 22% in the Global Warming Potential is achieved [16]. A detailed LCI and the Ecoinvent databases used in the analysis for the modelling of the energy sources used can be found on the research article [16].

3.2.2 Smart Carbon Separation and Carbon Capture Technologies (SCS-CCT)

The current scenario on Smart Carbon Separation and Carbon Capture Technologies (SCS-CCT) is still underdeveloped to be applied to large scale projects, because of poor expectations of financial returns, inconsistent and insufficient policy support, technological uncertainties, and a complex value-chain system [56]. However, while CO₂ emissions from the combustion of the fuel can only be saved if they are replaced by greener fuels (such as biomass), CO₂ emissions resulting from the decomposition of the limestone (around 65% of the total emissions), can only be avoided by carbon capture technologies (CCT). Post pyrolysis CCT are of specific interest in the case of the lime industry, and they are being developed to reduce the emissions of the calcination process. There are different routes for carbon capture that can be applied in the lime industry, ranging from very well-developed solvent-based technologies to the indirect heating of the raw meal to capture the unavoidable CO₂ emissions (Calix's Direct Separation Technology, CDST) [57]. For a specific review of several available CCT the reader is referred to Simoni et al[28].

The CDST kiln is a very promising technology as it requires minimal changes to the conventional process in the lime industry [57]. Regarding the working principle, calcite powder enters at the top of the kiln and the calcined product leaves the reactor at the bottom, while the CO₂ gaseous stream because of the Reaction 1 exits in counter-current flow the reactor. The main benefit of the technology is that the combustion gases are not mixed with the CO₂ from the decomposition of calcite, and mostly CO₂ is generated, avoiding complicated purification steps.

Recently, the International Energy Agency has discussed the alternative of using CO₂ in several industries. They state that the carbon in CO₂ enables the conversion of hydrogen into a fuel that is easier to handle and use and that CO₂ can also replace fossil fuels as raw material in chemicals and polymers [58]. Therefore, there is no doubt that if the purity of the obtained CO₂ is sufficient, not only avoided emissions but also revenues can be obtained. Even though the market for CO₂ at this moment is still in development, early opportunities can be cultivated, and CDST is an interesting technology for that purpose.

*CSDT: Calix's direct separation technology; HE: Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger; CP: 2-stage compressor

Figure 6. Combined carbon capture system for CO₂ purification and heat recovery (intermediate treatment)

To illustrate this scenario through the process-oriented methodology, consider the CDST shown in Figure 6 in which an intermediate treatment for the CO₂ is provided. In this case study, the parametrized LCI presented in Section 3.2.1 in Table 2 (case of natural gas) is expanded to consider the extra unit processes required for the purification of the CO₂ from calcite decomposition. Here, we show how to apply the methodology to model the intermediate treatment of Figure 6 (Following Figure 3). It is relevant to mention that there are no available databases to model these kinds of treatments and therefore, the feasibility of modelling the LCI through the proposed methodology is a significant advantage.

The system boundaries include now the kiln, the heat exchanger and the compressor, being the last two devices the intermediate treatment to prepare CO₂ to storage or use (Figure 6). The functional unit is still the production of 1 ton of CaO. The first unit process of the intermediate treatment is a heat exchanger, used to cool down the CO₂ gaseous stream leaving the kiln at 1173.15 K and to recover part of the intrinsic thermal energy of the stream. The heat exchanger is designed considering (1) the flow of CO₂ (790 kg/h, Table 2) leaves the reactor at 1173.15 K and needs to be cooled down to 273.15 K, and (2) water at 273.15 K is used as heat exchanger medium, changing from liquid to vapor state (2260 kJ/kg) and entering the heating system of the kiln at 1173.15 K. Below the calculation of the UPMI and UPEI for the intermediate treatment are shown.

UPMI and UPEI calculation

Following the Figure 3, first the material flows are determined. To calculate the required amount of water input to cool down the CO₂ stream, the energy balance assumes that all the heat from the CO₂ stream is transferred to the water.

$$Q_{H_2O} = Q_{CO_2}$$

$$Q_{H_2O(l)sensible} + Q_{H_2O(l)latent} + Q_{H_2O(v)sensible} = Q_{CO_2(g)sensible}$$

$$m_{H_2O}cp_{H_2O}\Delta T + m_{H_2O}\lambda_v + m_{H_2O}cp_{H_2O}\Delta T = m_{CO_2}cp_{CO_2}\Delta T$$

$$m_{H_2O} \left[4.18 \frac{kJ}{kgK} (373.15 - 298.18)K + 2260 \frac{kJ}{kg} + 1.99 \frac{kJ}{kgK} (1173.15 - 373.15)K \right] = 790kg \cdot 0.84 \frac{kJ}{kgK} (1173.15 - 298.18)K$$

$$m_{H_2O} = 128 \text{ kg}$$

In the heat exchanger, 790 kg of CO₂ are cooled down by 128 kg H₂O and all material flows are determined. For the calculation of the UPEI, the water vapor is reinserted in the heating system of the kiln. The total energy that can be theoretically transferred is

$$Q_{CO_2} = m_{CO_2} c_{pCO_2} \Delta T = 790 \text{ kg} \cdot 0.84 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgK}} (1173.15 - 298.18) \text{ K} = 580.63 \text{ MJ}$$

Besides the thermal energy that can be credited, the UPEI can be complemented by the electricity consumption of the heat exchanger (Point 3.1, Figure 3). Considering that the heat exchanger should deal with high pressures because of the gaseous states of the streams, a Shell and Tube Heat exchanger is recommended. Such heat exchangers can deal with biphasic flows; high and low pressures and they are compact and efficient. For simplicity we do not elaborate further but by knowing basic parameters such as material flows, state, etc. electricity consumption of the device can be obtained from a catalogue (e.g., <https://www.funke.de/>).

In compressor design, material balances are not necessary, and the focus is primarily on determining the UPEI. After the CO₂ is cooled down, 790 kg of CO₂ needs to be further processed for storage. For the specified flow, the electricity consumption of a 2-stage compressor is 1.3 MWh/Mt CO₂ (Point 3.1, Figure 3) according to an ASCO device (<https://www.ascoco2.com/>). The total electricity requirement considering the amount of processed CO₂ is 1.027 kWh.

Aggregated LCI data

Table 3 presents the parametrized LCI of the CSDT with heat recovery system (Figure 6).

Table 3. Inventory of the combined calcination and CO₂ recovery of lime production

		PROCESSED AMOUNT		ALLOCATION	COMMENT	
	OPERATION	FLOW	AMOUNT	UNIT		
INPUT	Calcination	CaCO ₃ from "CaCO ₃ preparation"	1.79	t	-	See Figure 4
		Shaft kiln Operation	3320	MJ	-	3900 MJ -580 MJ credit heat exchanger
	Heat exchanger	Water	0.13	t	-	
	Compressor	Electricity consumption	1.027	kWh		
OUTPUTS	OPERATION	FLOW	AMOUNT	UNIT	MASS	
		CaO (determining product)	1	t	0.56	
		CO ₂ (as co-product)	0.79	t	0.44	Decarbonation of CaCO ₃
		CO ₂ (as emission)	0.20			Fuel combustion (Natural gas)
	Emissions heating system					
	Water vapor (as emission)	0.13	t			

Despite its seemingly simplistic nature, this example yields several significant insights regarding the decarbonization of the lime industry. First, around 65% of the total emissions can be captured ([16])

and the total energy consumption of the lime kiln can be reduced by around 15% through the recovery of 580 MJ of energy from the CO₂ stream. The immediate result is that the fuel required and the consequent CO₂ emissions of the fuel combustion diminish as well (as discussed in Section 3.2.1). In particular, with the traditional PFRK (heat requirement 3900 MJ) fuelled by natural gas, 0.23 tCO₂/tCaO were released. However, with the savings of the CSDT system, the emissions are 0.20 tCO₂/tCaO, representing a 13% reduction in comparison to the previous scenario. Further decarbonization could be achieved by changing the fuel mix (Section 3.2.1). Finally, the proposing system shows potentiality to obtain pure CO₂ with further economic value as discussed before. Under this hypothesis, the CO₂ from CaCO₃ decomposition could be potentially considered no longer as an emission but as a by-product of the CaO production [58]. As a result, part of the environmental load of CaO production could be allocated to CO₂ production. For instance, if a mass allocation procedure is applied, all the emissions from “CaCO₃ extraction” until “Calcination”(Figure 4) would be allocated 56% to CaO and 44% to CO₂ (Table 3).

This limited example aims at showing how to model the unit processes through the methodology described in Figure 3, while emphasizing the ground-breaking idea of considering CO₂ no longer as a problem but as an opportunity of cost reduction. With regards to the costs, within the EU emissions allowance, the cost of emitted carbon by the industries can be significant and in the last 4 years, it has incremented 9 times [59]. According to the European Central Bank in 2018 it was 10 € per metric ton of carbon and in 2022 90 € per metric ton of carbon[20]. Considering the carbon price in 2022, for the case in which natural gas is used the carbon cost would be 91,8 €/tCaO (Table 2). However, by applying the CDST system (Table 3) a reduction of around 85% in the carbon taxes can be obtained. Furthermore, the recovery of pure CO₂ encourages the exploration of further market integration with potential revenues for the lime industry.

3.3 Case study 3: Use of wastepaper mill sludge in a lime plaster manufacturing

In this section we focus mainly on the modelling of supplementary materials as specified in Figure 3, Step 2.2. In the context of circular economy, the idea of supplementary materials is to reduce the extraction of virgin raw materials (Figure 4), by looping in a closed or open cycle the materials at the end of life. In particular, the case study deals with the open upcycling of paper mill sludge. This residue is generated during the treatment of waste water in paper production and can potentially be used in a lime-based plaster manufacturing, replacing the extraction of calcite. The application of the substitution modelling to calculate the life cycle inventory of the intermediate treatment is shown below.

Feasibility analysis and provider data collection

Figure 7 shows the system boundaries of the Life Cycle 1 (production of paper) and the upcycling Life Cycle 2 in which PMS is reinserted for the lime-based plaster production. In the waste water treatment, the effluent should be cauterized by using CaO, which reacts with soda ash (Na₂CO₃) and produces caustic soda (NaOH) along with CaCO₃ (lime sludge) as a waste material [60], [61]. Once the waste is treated, the most common practice has always been the landfilling disposal of the sludge (around 70% of the total generated) [62], [63]. Therefore, it is fair to consider PMS as a waste.

In a real case, the cooperation between the paper industry and the plasters industry would be desirable to determine how much PMS could be provided. This collaboration between stakeholders is a key aspect to ensure the sustainable development of the construction materials. However, it is also possible to make some previous theoretical estimations. In terms of production of paper and pulp mill sludge, around 40 to 50 kg of sludge (70% primary sludge and 30% secondary sludge) is generated in the production of 1 tons of paper at a paper mill [64]. In 2020 in Europe around 8,5E7 t of paper and board were produced and the market is dominated by Germany (25.1%) [65] and the

overall daily production of paper and board in Germany is 0,059 Mt. Assuming equal capacities of the plants, on average this value could be divided by the total amount of factories in Germany (160) to estimate a reference flow of the paper and board production for the Life Cycle 1 (372.6 t/d) [65]. Then considering the daily production and the ratio of sludge-to-paper, the maximum availability of the paper mill sludge of the Life Cycle 1 in Germany per reference flow of is 18.6 t_{sludge}/day.

Figure 7. Simplified process of paper mill sludge generation (Life Cycle 1, secondary resource) and lime-based plaster manufacturing (Life Cycle 2, determining product)

Determination of the relevant properties of the waste

The feasibility of the recycling depends on the physical and chemical properties of the PMS. With respect to the chemical composition, to have a snapshot of the ranges in which the mineralogical composition of the PMS can vary, literature was researched, and Table 4 is provided. Average moisture of the PMS, pH, and amount of organics are reported in the same Table and used for the LCI calculation. In general, the chemical composition of the sludge is relatively close to the one of Hydrated Lime and therefore the feasibility of its replacement is supported. The moisture and the organics content need to be considered for the process design, as they have to be removed and therefore energy will be consumed to power the intermediate treatment process for the conditioning.

Table 4. Chemical composition of Paper Mill Sludge, Hydrated Lime, and Portland Cement

	Component (wt.%)	Paper mill sludge (PMS) [66]–[71] [72] [69] [63] [73]	PMS (assumed)	Hydrated Lime Commercial [74]
Mineralogical composition (dry base)	SiO ₂	2 – 20	15	0.13
	Al ₂ O ₃	0.8 – 5	2.5	0.06
	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.25 – 2.5	-	0.07
	CaO	16 – 90	75	98.53
	MgO	0.2 – 10	5	1.09
	Others	0 – 0.3	-	0.25
Physical parameters	Moisture (%)	28.4 ± 11.0	20	-
	pH	7.3 ± 1.8	7	-
	Organics	34.9 ± 21.1	40	-

Determination of the functionality performance

As the PMS is intended to be used as replacement of hydrated lime, the content of portlandite is used to account for the functionality performance. The maximum amount of portlandite that can be produced is calculated considering the assumed chemical composition (75% CaO) and the only reaction occurring is the lime slaking (Reaction 2).

The percentages of portlandite can be considered equal to the percentages of CaO (Table 4) and the substitutability is calculated as follows

$$\alpha^{sr:disp} = \frac{[Ca(OH)_2]^{sr}}{[Ca(OH)_2]^{disp}} = \frac{0.75}{0.98} = 0.765$$

The substitutability would be equal to 1 in the case that the recycled material can provide as much hydrated lime as the substituted material.

Design of the intermediate treatment

After being transported to the plant, PMS must be conditioned to remove the initial humidity (20% of the total mass) and the organic matter (40% dry mass) according to Table 4. Previous studies have shown it can be removed by pyrolysis and that the main mass loss attributed to the decomposition of the organic matter in PMS takes place between 300-400 °C [75], [76]. The next step, after removing the humidity and the organic matter is the thermal activation of the PMS, which occurs at around 700-800°C. The water removal, organic material removal and calcium oxide synthesis process is modelled by a lime kiln. The energy requirements of the lime kiln were based on a previous work [16]. The main emissions associated to the raw materials during the calcination step are water vapor and carbon dioxide. The last one is divided in CO₂ from the calcite decomposition (Reaction 1) and organic matter decomposition (Reaction 3) and they were calculated as the stoichiometric amount resulting from the chemical reactions and the amounts defined in Table 4.

After the calcination, the calcined PMS is mostly CaO (PMS-D) and is hydrated using a lime hydrator, the energy requirements of which are also based on a previous work [16]. For simplification the UPMI and UPEI calculation are not shown and Table 5 summarizes the LCI of the Intermediate Treatment of PMS, to produce a recycled hydrated lime (RHL).

Calculation of the substitutability amount

The technical substitution potential is calculated as follows according to Equation 4. The substitutability was calculated before. In the case of the Resource potential, the maximum amount to be inserted in the intermediate treatment is 18,6 t PMS/d and the effective amount to be used as replacement of the original resource is 1 t of RHL/2.02 t of PMS (Table 5). Therefore, the Resource potential is 9.20 t and the technical substitution potential is 7.04 t. From a practical point, the technical substitution implies that 9,2 t of the RHL are equivalent to 7,04 t of HL. Assuming that the functionality performance of the secondary resource is acceptable, this amount represents the maximum quantity of the transformed secondary resource that is available per reference flow of the Life Cycle 1 to be reinserted in the Life Cycle 2.

Table 5. Life Cycle Inventory of the intermediate treatment processes of PMS to produce recycled hydrated lime (Life Cycle 2)

Operation/ process modelled		Processed amount		Inventory Amount		Sources & Notes
<i>Process Step: Pyrolysis</i>						
Input	PMS	2.02	t	1	t	
	Transportation	338	tkm	200	km	Assumed
	Kiln fuel consumption	4461.6	MJ	2640	MJ/t PMS	Laveglia et al. [16]
Output	PMS-D	0.81	t	-	-	
	Water vapor (as emission)	0.40	t	0.2	t H ₂ O/t PMS	Calculated stoichiometrically (Humidity 20%)
	CO₂ (as emission)	2.46	t	1.46	t CO ₂ /t PMS	Assumed 40% organic matter (Reaction 3, do not count as emissions)
	CO₂ (as emission)	0.48	t	0.28	t CO ₂ /t PMS	Calculated stoichiometrically (Reaction 1)
	CO₂ (as emission)	0.26	t		55.9 t CO ₂ /TJ	Fuel combustion (Natural Gas)
<i>Process Step: Lime slaking</i>						
Input	PMS-D	0.81	t			
	Water	0.19	t	0.32	t H ₂ O/t CaO	Calculated stoichiometrically (75% CaO, Table 6)
	Hydrator Electricity operation	0.35	kW	0.35	kW/t	Laveglia et al. [16]
Output	RHL	1	t			

The reference flows of the Life Cycle 1 and 2 should be considered at the same time to determine the real influence of this value on the inventory of the determining product, in this case a lime plaster. If the amount that can be substituted is significant or not, depends on the process demand of Life Cycle

2 (production capacity of the plant). To illustrate this concept, consider the reference flow of Life Cycle 1 (368.75 $t_{\text{paper/d}}$; 18.63 $t_{\text{sludge/d}}$) and the LCI of Life Cycle 2 in Table 5 (based on Figure 7). Three alternatives of reference flows are evaluated in Table 6, keeping in all of them the mixing ratio 1:3 Hydrated Lime:Sand. First, case A represents no substitution of hydrated lime (base case) with a reference flow of 100 t/d. Case B and C include a substitution of Hydrated Lime by the Recycled HL, with two different reference flows (100 t/d and 250 t/d). As the reference flow of the Life Cycle 2 increases, the potential benefit of the substitution diminishes from 28% (case B, 7 $t_{\text{sludge/25 } t_{\text{binder}}}$) to around 11% (case C, 7 $t_{\text{sludge/62.5 } t_{\text{binder}}}$), because even though the proportion binder:aggregate is fixed, more binder and aggregate is produced to satisfy the increased reference flow.

Table 6. Life Cycle Inventory of the lime-plaster production and effect substituting hydrated lime by RHL

Operation / process modelled		A. No substitution		B. Max substitution		C. Max substitution	
Process step: Mixing							
Input	Hydrated Lime	25	t	18	t	55.5	t
	Sand	75	t	75	t	187.5	t
	RHL	-	-	7	t	7	t
Output (Reference flow)	Lime Plaster	100	t	100	t	250	t

3.4 Decarbonizing the lime-based construction materials industry

The lime industry's carbon dioxide emissions are mainly concentrated in the calcination process, where CaCO_3 is converted to CaO . Approximately 0.79 $\text{tCO}_2/\text{t CaO}$ emissions are inevitable due to the decomposition of calcium carbonate (65% of the total emissions). Additional CO_2 is generated from fuel combustion in the kiln, and the emissions vary depending on the fuel mix used [16].

Figure 8. Effect of strategies on carbon reduction potential for decarbonizing lime-based construction materials industry.

Sections 3.1 to 3.3 demonstrate three strategies to reduce CO_2 emissions: carbon direct avoidance, carbon capture and circular economy. These strategies can be implemented in various ways and require a flexible and rigorous methodology. The process-oriented methodology developed in this paper enables the successful application of these strategies, considering different production contexts and scenarios. It allows for independent calculations based on scientific parameters, rather than relying solely on generic databases. The developed methodology offers freedom to LCA

practitioners and facilitates the implementation of diverse decarbonization pathways. Figure 8 summarizes significant insights and lessons learned from the case studies conducted in this research.

Carbon capture and heat recovery through smart separation technology

The design based on a smart separation of CO₂ aims at taking advantage of each possibility to reduce CO₂. In the best case, 0.79 tCO₂/tCaO from calcite decomposition can be captured. Furthermore, for the preparation of CaO, fuel has been burned to decompose the calcite, and the exhaust CO₂ brings along thermal energy that can be recovered. By implementing a heat exchanger in the intermediate treatment for the CO₂ stream, 533 MJ could be credited in the total energy consumption of the lime kiln. This represents 15% reduction in the total energy consumed (3367 – 3900 MJ/tCaO) and 13% (0.20 - 0.23 tCO₂/tCaO) reduction comparing scenarios with and without the technology. Furthermore, given the further use of pure CO₂ as raw material in other industries, in the future and if this technology is applied, it could be considered a by-product and no longer an emission. As a result, part of the environmental load of CaO production can be allocated to CO₂ production, reducing the total environmental impact of the lime-based construction materials. The latter option can also have economic implications for the industry, because of the reduction in carbon taxes (up to 85%) and additional revenues could be obtained by the selling of the CO₂.

Carbon direct avoidance: more efficient kilns and sustainable energy sources

In this paper the effect of the operational energy on the overall energy consumption for CaO manufacturing has been analysed. The preferred technology in Europe is a PFRK kiln because it requires 3900 MJ/tCaO vs around 6100 MJ/tCaO for the less efficient LRK technology (40% reduction in the total energy consumption). The technology of the kiln plays a significant role for the total CO₂ emitted, because by reducing the total energy consumption of the device, less fuel is required. In particular, the emissions of the fuel combustion depend on the fuel mix, because each has a specific carbon intensity factor. For the same energy consumption, if natural gas is used instead of lignite for CaO production, a 17% reduction in the total CO₂ emitted is obtained. This reduction can be up to 22% if a combination of eco-efficient fuels including biomass is used.

Circular economy: use of alternative raw materials

Although the circular economy concept is useful to preserve the virgin materials from its extraction, it does not always lead to significant CO₂ reduction. In the case of lime-based materials, the main problem is that the emissions from CaCO₃ decomposition are a big share in the total CO₂ and they cannot be avoided. In order to be used as supplementary materials, the waste or by-products should have a similar chemical composition as hydrated lime (i.e., amount of CaO) and the same nature of emissions would be expected when they are calcined. The type and number of intermediate treatments for the conditioning of the waste or by-product and the transportation required can limit the potential credits obtained. In the case of PMS, 60% of the material is organics and water, therefore more PMS needs to be processed to obtain the CaO required for Hydrated Lime preparation (1.44 t CaCO₃/t Ca(OH)₂ vs 2.02 t PMS/t Ca(OH)₂). As a result, the energy consumption in the kiln is around 12% more and the CO₂ of the fuel combustion is incremented by 23%. However, the specific emissions of the calcite decomposition in PMS are around 20% (0.60 and 0.48 t CO₂/t Ca(OH)₂) lower because of the reduced CaCO₃ content in the PMS ($\alpha^{sr:disp} = 0.765$, Section 3.3). Focusing only on the calcination operation, the expected reduction by using PMS in comparison to the traditional manufacturing of hydrated lime (natural gas fuel) is around 9% [16].

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a new framework for calculating a parametrized life cycle inventory (LCI) for lime-based materials manufacturing, incorporating process and materials design principles. Through three case studies, the successful implementation of three decarbonization strategies is demonstrated, leading to the following conclusions:

- CO₂ emissions in lime-based materials manufacturing are primarily concentrated in the calcination operation, with 0.79 tCO₂/tCaO being unavoidable due to calcite decomposition. Additional CO₂ emissions are influenced by fuel combustion in the kiln. Among the three decarbonization strategies discussed, carbon capture offers the highest potential for carbon reduction, followed by carbon direct avoidance and circular economy approaches.
- The choice of lime kiln technology significantly impacts total CO₂ emissions, as reducing energy consumption in the kiln reduces the need for fuel. The preferred technology, such as the Parallel Flow Regenerative Kiln consumes 40% less energy compared to less efficient options like the Long Rotary Kiln. Using natural gas instead of lignite as fuel can further reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 17%.
- Implementing a direct separation technology for CO₂ capture from calcite decomposition can capture 0.79 tCO₂/tCaO in the best-case scenario. When combined with thermal energy recovery, it reduces kiln energy consumption by 15% and CO₂ emissions by 13%. The purity of captured CO₂ and its potential for use as a raw material in other markets make it a potential by-product in the future. The reduction in CO₂ emissions also has economic implications, as it can reduce carbon taxes by up to 85%, contributing to the economic sustainability.
- The use of supplementary raw materials for binder production in lime-based construction materials has the most limited effect of the analysed strategies, primarily due to the high and unavoidable CO₂ emissions from calcite decomposition. Using paper mill sludge as a replacement for hydrated lime in lime-based plaster manufacturing can reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 9%, depending on the intermediate treatment required.
- The parametrized LCI modelling methodology presented in this paper provides greater autonomy to LCA practitioners by reducing reliance on generic databases. It incorporates scientific principles and transparent parameterization, enabling practitioners to calculate methodologically sound and well-grounded inventories. However, it requires a background in process engineering, detailed documentation of assumptions, and validation with industry data whenever possible.

Acknowledgements

This research has been carried out within the framework of the EU SUBLime network. This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie project SUBLime [Grant Agreement n°955986]

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Agustin Laveglia: Conceptualization, Methodology, LCI calculations and analysis, discussion, Writing – original draft, paper preparation, Writing – review & editing, results, and discussion. Neven Ukrainczyk: Resources, Writing – review & editing, results and discussion, Supervision. Nele De Belie: Writing – review & editing, results and discussion, Supervision. Eddie Koenders: Resources, Writing – review & editing, results and discussion, Supervision.

References

- [1] ISO, "14044: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines," *Bmj*, vol. 332, no. 7555, p. 1418.1, 2006, doi: 10.1136/bmj.332.7555.1418.
- [2] C. Jiménez, M. Barra, A. Josa, and S. Valls, "LCA of recycled and conventional concretes designed using the Equivalent Mortar Volume and classic methods," *Constr Build Mater*, vol. 84, pp. 245–252, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2015.03.051.
- [3] M. U. Hossain, C. S. Poon, I. M. C. Lo, and J. C. P. Cheng, "Comparative LCA on using waste materials in the cement industry: A Hong Kong case study," *Resour Conserv Recycl*, vol. 120, pp. 199–208, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.12.012.
- [4] M. Kamali, K. Hewage, and R. Sadiq, "Conventional versus modular construction methods: A comparative cradle-to-gate LCA for residential buildings," *Energy Build*, vol. 204, p. 109479, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.109479.
- [5] P. Van den Heede and N. De Belie, "Sustainability assessment of potentially 'green' concrete types using life cycle assessment," in *Sustainable and Nonconventional Construction Materials using Inorganic Bonded Fiber Composites*, Elsevier, 2017, pp. 235–263. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-102001-2.00010-3.
- [6] P. van den Heede, A. Mignon, G. Habert, and N. de Belie, "Cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment of self-healing engineered cementitious composite with in-house developed (semi-)synthetic superabsorbent polymers," *Cem Concr Compos*, vol. 94, pp. 166–180, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2018.08.017.
- [7] D. Rodríguez-Robles, P. Van Den Heede, and N. De Belie, "Life cycle assessment applied to recycled aggregate concrete," in *New Trends in Eco-efficient and Recycled Concrete*, Elsevier, 2018, pp. 207–256. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-102480-5.00009-9.
- [8] A. Josa, A. Aguado, A. Cardim, and E. Byars, "Comparative analysis of the life cycle impact assessment of available cement inventories in the EU," *Cem Concr Res*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 781–788, May 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2007.02.004.
- [9] J. Juhart, G. A. David, M. R. M. Saade, C. Baldermann, A. Passer, and F. Mittermayr, "Functional and environmental performance optimization of Portland cement-based materials by combined mineral fillers," *Cem Concr Res*, vol. 122, pp. 157–178, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2019.05.001.
- [10] K. L. Scrivener, V. M. John, and E. M. Gartner, "Eco-efficient cements: Potential economically viable solutions for a low-CO₂ cement-based materials industry," *Cem Concr Res*, vol. 114, no. February, pp. 2–26, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2018.03.015.
- [11] S. A. Miller, V. M. John, S. A. Pacca, and A. Horvath, "Carbon dioxide reduction potential in the global cement industry by 2050," *Cem Concr Res*, vol. 114, pp. 115–124, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2017.08.026.
- [12] E. Gartner and H. Hirao, "A review of alternative approaches to the reduction of CO₂ emissions associated with the manufacture of the binder phase in concrete," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 78. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 126–142, Dec. 01, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2015.04.012.
- [13] Laveglia, A., Sambataro, L., Ukrainczyk, N., Oertel, T., De Belie, N., Koenders, E., How to improve the cradle-to-gate environmental and economic sustainability in lime-based construction

materials? Answers from a real-life case-study, *Developments in the Built Environment* (2023), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dibe.2023.100186>

[14] E. L. Association, "INNOVATION IN THE LIME SECTOR 2.0 Innovation that delivers on sustainability," 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eula.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Innovation-in-the-Lime-sector-2.0-.pdf>

[15] European Commission, *Competitiveness of the European Cement and Lime Sectors*. 2018. [Online]. Available: https://www.wifo.ac.at/jart/prj3/wifo/resources/person_dokument/person_dokument.jart?publikationsid=61003&mime_type=application/pdf

[16] A. Laveglia, L. Sambataro, N. Ukrainczyk, N. De Belie, and E. Koenders, "Hydrated lime life-cycle assessment: Current and future scenarios in four EU countries," *J Clean Prod*, vol. 369, p. 133224, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133224.

[17] F. Pietro Campo, C. Tua, L. Biganzoli, S. Pantini, and M. Grosso, "Natural and enhanced carbonation of lime in its different applications: a review," *Environmental Technology Reviews*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 224–237, 2021, doi: 10.1080/21622515.2021.1982023.

[18] A. Sagastume Gutiérrez, J. Van Caneghem, J. B. Cogollos Martínez, and C. Vandecasteele, "Evaluation of the environmental performance of lime production in Cuba," *J Clean Prod*, vol. 31, pp. 126–136, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.02.035.

[19] European Commission, *BAT document for the production of Cement, Lime, and Magnesium Oxide*. 2013. doi: 10.2788/12850.

[20] E. Central Bank, "Economic Bulletin Issue 3, 2022." [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/ecbu/eb202203.en.pdf>

[21] E. L. Association. "Lime as a Natural Carbon Sink: Examples of mineral carbonation in lime applications". Report. 2021. [Online]. Available: https://www.kalk.de/fileadmin/Home/Wissensportal/Pressemitteilungen/2021/EuLA_Carbonation_Booklet_Lime_As_A_Natural_Carbon_Sink_01.pdf

[22] G. Cultrone, E. Sebastián, and M. O. Huertas, "Forced and natural carbonation of lime-based mortars with and without additives: Mineralogical and textural changes," *Cem Concr Res*, vol. 35, no. 12, pp. 2278–2289, Dec. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2004.12.012.

[23] M. Lassinantti Gualtieri, M. Romagnoli, P. Miselli, M. Cannio, and A. F. Gualtieri, "Full quantitative phase analysis of hydrated lime using the Rietveld method," *Cem Concr Res*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 1273–1279, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2012.05.016.

[24] T. Schlegel and A. Shtiza, "Environmental footprint study of mortars , renders and plasters formulations with no , low or high hydrated lime content," *International Masonry Conference 2014*, no. July, pp. 1–10, 2014.

[25] J. Diaz-Basteris, J. C. Sacramento Rivero, and B. Menéndez, "Life cycle assessment of restoration mortars and binders," *Constr Build Mater*, vol. 326, no. December 2021, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.126863.

[26] M. Antonia, K. Christopher, K. Maria, A. Eleni, B. Asterios, and D. Aris, "Life Cycle Analysis of Mortars and its Environmental Impact," *MRS Online Proceedings Library*, vol. 895, no. 1, p. 602, 2006, doi: 10.1557/PROC-0895-G06-02.

- [27] G. M. Cuenca-Moyano, S. Zanni, A. Bonoli, and I. Valverde-Palacios, "Development of the life cycle inventory of masonry mortar made of natural and recycled aggregates," *J Clean Prod*, vol. 140, pp. 1272–1286, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.10.029.
- [28] M. Simoni, M. D. Wilkes, S. Brown, J. L. Provis, H. Kinoshita, and T. Hanein, "Decarbonising the lime industry: State-of-the-art," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 168. Elsevier Ltd, Oct. 01, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.112765.
- [29] S. Kamalakkannan and A. K. Kulatunga, "Optimization of eco-design decisions using a parametric life cycle assessment," *Sustain Prod Consum*, vol. 27, pp. 1297–1316, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2021.03.006.
- [30] K. K. Weththasinghe, A. Stephan, V. Francis, and P. Tiwari, "Improving material selection in shopping centres through a parametric life cycle embodied flow and material cost analysis model," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 165, no. April, p. 112530, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.112530.
- [31] Z. Alwan, A. Nawarathna, R. Ayman, M. Zhu, and Y. ElGhazi, "Framework for parametric assessment of operational and embodied energy impacts utilising BIM," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 42, no. January, p. 102768, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jobbe.2021.102768.
- [32] J. Zhang, G. Liu, B. Chen, D. Song, J. Qi, and X. Liu, "Analysis of CO₂ Emission for the cement manufacturing with alternative raw materials: A LCA-based framework," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 61, pp. 2541–2545, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.12.041.
- [33] S. C. Galusnyak, L. Petrescu, and C. C. Cormos, "Environmental impact assessment of post-combustion CO₂ capture technologies applied to cement production plants," *J Environ Manage*, vol. 320, no. August, p. 115908, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115908.
- [34] M. Georgiades, I. Hussain, B. Steubing, C. Cheeseman, and J. Myers, "Resources , Conservation & Recycling Prospective life cycle assessment of European cement production," *Resour Conserv Recycl*, vol. 194, no. December 2022, p. 106998, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.106998.
- [35] C. Chen, G. Habert, Y. Bouzidi, A. Jullien, and A. Ventura, "LCA allocation procedure used as an incitative method for waste recycling: An application to mineral additions in concrete," *Resour Conserv Recycl*, vol. 54, no. 12, pp. 1231–1240, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2010.04.001.
- [36] G. Habert, J. B. D'Espinose De Lacaillerie, and N. Roussel, "An environmental evaluation of geopolymer based concrete production: Reviewing current research trends," *J Clean Prod*, vol. 19, no. 11, pp. 1229–1238, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.03.012.
- [37] M. Pavlíková et al., "Valorization of wood chips ash as an eco-friendly mineral admixture in mortar mix design," *Waste Management*, vol. 80, pp. 89–100, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2018.09.004.
- [38] W. Xing, V. W. Tam, K. N. Le, J. L. Hao, and J. Wang, "Life cycle assessment of sustainable concrete with recycled aggregate and supplementary cementitious materials," *Resour Conserv Recycl*, vol. 193, no. August 2022, p. 106947, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.106947.
- [39] ISO, "14040: Environmental management—life cycle assessment—Principles and framework," International organization for standardization, vol. 2006, 2006.
- [40] "Model for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of buildings EFIResources: Resource Efficient Construction towards Sustainable Design," 2018, doi: 10.2760/10016.

- [41] J. H. Arehart, J. Hart, F. Pomponi, and B. D'Amico, "Carbon sequestration and storage in the built environment," *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, vol. 27. Elsevier B.V., pp. 1047–1063, Jul. 01, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2021.02.028.
- [42] R. Frischknecht et al., "Overview and Methodology," *ecoinvent Centre*, no. 1, pp. 1–77, 2007, [Online]. Available: http://www.ecoinvent.org/fileadmin/documents/en/01_OverviewAndMethodology.pdf
- [43] V. G. Larsen, N. Tollin, P. A. Sattrup, M. Birkved, and T. Holmboe, "What are the challenges in assessing circular economy for the built environment? A literature review on integrating LCA, LCC and S-LCA in life cycle sustainability assessment, LCSA," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 50. Elsevier Ltd, Jun. 01, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.job.2022.104203.
- [44] C. Vadenbo, S. Hellweg, and T. F. Astrup, "Let's Be Clear(er) about Substitution: A Reporting Framework to Account for Product Displacement in Life Cycle Assessment," *J Ind Ecol*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 1078–1089, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1111/jiec.12519.
- [45] "B DIRECTIVE 2008/98/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (Text with EEA relevance)." Directive. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02008L0098-20180705&from=SV>
- [46] S. Toniolo, A. Mazzi, C. Pieretto, and A. Scipioni, "Allocation strategies in comparative life cycle assessment for recycling: Considerations from case studies," *Resour Conserv Recycl*, vol. 117, pp. 249–261, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.10.011.
- [47] World Bank Group, "Environmental, Health, and Safety Guidelines for Cement and Lime Manufacturing," Technical reference document. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/zh/681871489639027962/pdf/113555-WP-ENGLISH-Cement-and-Lime-Manufacturing-PUBLIC.pdf>
- [48] EuLA, "A Competitive and Efficient Lime industry: Cornerstone for a Sustainable Europe". Technical Report. 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.eula.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/A-Competitive-and-Efficient-Lime-Industry-Technical-report-by-Ecofys_0.pdf
- [49] Navigant, "Gas for Climate. The optimal role for gas in a net-zero emissions energy system" Navigant Netherlands B.V., no. March, p. 231, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://gasforclimate2050.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Navigant-Gas-for-Climate-The-optimal-role-for-gas-in-a-net-zero-emissions-energy-system-March-2019.pdf>
- [50] M. Eriksson, "Sustainability measures in quicklime and cement clinker production." Thesis. 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:882932/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- [51] M. Bustillo Revuelta, "Lime," in *Construction Materials: Geology, Production and Applications*, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021, pp. 167–193. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-65207-4_7.
- [52] E. Kawai, A. Ozawa, and B. D. Leibowicz, "Role of carbon capture and utilization (CCU) for decarbonization of industrial sector: A case study of Japan," *Appl Energy*, vol. 328, p. 120183, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120183.
- [53] S. Bajpai et al., "Opportunities, challenges and the way ahead for carbon capture, utilization and sequestration (CCUS) by the hydrocarbon industry: Towards a sustainable future," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 15595–15616, Nov. 01, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.egyr.2022.11.023.

- [54] S. Guillén-Lambea, R. Abrahão, and M. Carvalho, "Life cycle assessment of power generation systems in Spain: Exploring a broader view from a consequential perspective," *Sustain Prod Consum*, vol. 38, pp. 28–40, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2023.03.018.
- [55] German Environment Agency, "CO2 Emission Factors for Fossil Fuels,". Emission Situation. 2016. [Online]. Available: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1968/publikationen/co2_emission_factors_for_fossil_fuels_correction.pdf
- [56] G. Cabrera, A. Dickson, A. D. Nimubona, and J. Quigley, "Carbon capture, utilisation and storage: Incentives, effects and policy," *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 120, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103756.
- [57] M. Greco-Coppi, C. Hofmann, J. Ströhle, D. Walter, and B. Epple, "Efficient CO2 capture from lime production by an indirectly heated carbonate looping process," *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 112, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2021.103430.
- [58] International Energy Agency, "Putting CO2 to Use: Creating value from emissions," Report. 2019. [Online]. Available: https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/50652405-26db-4c41-82dc-c23657893059/Putting_CO2_to_Use.pdf.
- [59] P. Bayer and M. el Aklın, "The European Union Emissions Trading System reduced CO 2 emissions despite low prices", doi: 10.1073/pnas.1918128117/-/DCSupplemental.y.
- [60] G. M. Dorris and L. H. Allen, "Effect of Reburned Lime Structure on the Rates of Slaking, Causticizing and Lime Mud Settling.," *Journal of Pulp and Paper Science*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 89–98, 1985. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289468614_Effects_of_liming_ratio_on_lime_mud_settling_and_filterability#fullTextFileContent
- [61] C. R. I. ENG, "Utilization of Lime Sludge for Value Reburning of Lime Sludge National Council for Cement and Building Materials New Delhi," *National Council for Cement and Building Material New Delhi*, no. March, 2000. [Online]. Available: <http://www.dcpulppaper.org/gifs/report32.pdf>
- [62] M. Likon and P. Trebe, "Recent Advances in Paper Mill Sludge Management," in *Industrial Waste, InTech*, 2012. doi: 10.5772/37043.
- [63] European Commission. "Best Available Techniques (BAT) reference document for the production of pulp, paper and board." *Industrial Emissions Directive 2010/75/EU*. 2015. [Online]. Available: https://eippcb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2019-11/PP_revised_BREF_2015.pdf
- [64] P. Bajpai, "Management of Pulp and Paper Mill Waste". 2015. Doi: /10.1007/978-3-319-11788-1
- [65] Confederation of European Paper Industries. "CEPI key statistics 2020: European pulp and paper industry" 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cepi.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Key-Statistics-2021-Final.pdf>
- [66] A. Yaras, "Combined effects of paper mill sludge and carbonation sludge on characteristics of fired clay bricks," *Constr Build Mater*, vol. 249, p. 118722, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.118722.
- [67] P. Vashistha, V. Kumar, S. K. Singh, D. Dutt, G. Tomar, and P. Yadav, "Valorization of paper mill lime sludge via application in building construction materials: A review," *Constr Build Mater*, vol. 211, pp. 371–382, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.03.085.

- [68] V. Sahu and V. Gayathri, "The Use of Fly Ash and Lime Sludge as Partial Replacement of Cement in Mortar," *International Journal of Engineering and Technology Innovation*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 30–37, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/228833526.pdf>
- [69] S. Yan, K. Sagoe-Crentsil, and G. Shapiro, "Reuse of de-inking sludge from wastepaper recycling in cement mortar products," *J Environ Manage*, vol. 92, no. 8, pp. 2085–2090, Aug. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2011.03.028.
- [70] S. D. Ingale and P. D. Nemade, "An investigation on fresh state properties of cement paste and concrete with GGBS and waste paper sludge ash," *Mater Today Proc*, vol. 65, pp. 1237–1242, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2022.04.183.
- [71] L. H. Buruberri, M. P. Seabra, and J. A. Labrincha, "Preparation of clinker from paper pulp industry wastes.," *J Hazard Mater*, vol. 286, pp. 252–60, 2015.
- [72] T. Turner, R. Wheeler, and I. W. Oliver, "Evaluating land application of pulp and paper mill sludge: A review," *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 317. Academic Press, Sep. 01, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115439.
- [73] R. Abdullah, C. F. Ishak, W. R. Kadir, and R. A. Bakar, "Characterization and feasibility assessment of recycled paper mill sludges for land application in relation to the environment," *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 9314–9329, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.3390/ijerph120809314.
- [74] F. A. Cardoso, H. C. Fernandes, R. G. Pileggi, M. A. Cincotto, and V. M. John, "Carbide lime and industrial hydrated lime characterization," *Powder Technol*, vol. 195, no. 2, pp. 143–149, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.powtec.2009.05.017.
- [75] G. Jaria, C. P. Silva, C. I. A. Ferreira, M. Otero, and V. Calisto, "Sludge from paper mill effluent treatment as raw material to produce carbon adsorbents: An alternative waste management strategy," *J Environ Manage*, vol. 188, pp. 203–211, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.12.004.
- [76] V. Calisto, C. I. A. Ferreira, S. M. Santos, M. V. Gil, M. Otero, and V. I. Esteves, "Production of adsorbents by pyrolysis of paper mill sludge and application on the removal of citalopram from water," *Bioresour Technol*, vol. 166, pp. 335–344, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2014.05.047.